

ASSORTMENT ANALYSIS OF BINDING MATERIALS USED IN SURGERY

Saidova M.O.
Ikramova G.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan.
e-mail: Saidovamadin2002@gmail.com phone number: +998 (91) 232-63-53
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Introduction: Improving the healthy lifestyle of citizens is considered as one of the foundations of social sector reforms in our country.

Pharmaceuticals as one of the priorities for the development of the social sector, as defined in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 the issues of further development of the industry, improvement of supply of cheap, high-quality medicines and medical supplies to the population and medical institutions, prevention of unjustified increase in the prices of medicines [1]

The purpose of the study: to compile a list of surgical bandages produced by local and international manufacturers and registered in the state register of drugs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Studying the share of local and foreign manufacturers of the binding agents based on the compiled list. At the same time, the study and comparison of the turnover, price, demand and possibilities of the means of binding in the current consumer market

Result: Bandages are different from other goods due to their widespread assortment in the current consumer market. There are **2094** assortments in the department of medical products for in vitro diagnostics, of which 219 are Bandages. Bandages O The market of Uzbekistan is entered by European, CIS(Commonwealth of Independent States) and local companies with their binding materials

COUNTRIES	VARIETY OF ASSORTMENT
Uzbekistan	149
CIS	23
European countries	47

When the assortment analysis was carried out by company, we got the following result, if we take this big rectangle as the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, the goods of these companies occupy the market in the following way.

When we analyze the variety of assortment in a large group of goods

Current market turnover, price, demand and possibilities of binding materials. Bandages, cotton, gauze and plasters are the most demanded groups of bandages. 3 local manufacturers (Elasticum OOO, Baxtteksfarm OOO, Makonmirzo OOO) of fasteners occupy the main place. These cover the market widely in terms of price and quality. Elasticum OOO is in the first place with its quality and price. The second one is Baxtteksfarm OOO and third one is Makonmirzo OOO, The last ones also famous for its quality, but their price is more higher than first one

Conclusion: So, in the analysis of the assortment of binding materials by countries (Uzbekistan, CIS and European countries), **68%** of the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan is made up of local production, **11%** of the CIS and **28%** of European imports. In production, the main places are occupied by various regions of the range (Bakhtteks-Farm OOO (**13**); Elastikum, OOO (**14**); FAZO-LUXE, OOO (**13**); Selkhoz mash Textil, OOO (**11**)). The assortment is divided into such types as bandages, belts, bandages, cotton, leucoplaster, gauze, plasters. In

the department of medical products for in vitro diagnostics, there are **2094** assortments, of which **219** are bandages.

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